

ANIMAL FARM: A RETRANSLATION PROPOSAL

Davi Silva Gonçalves

Midwest State University - Unicentro
Center of Slavistics
Brazil

Abstract

After entering our public domain, George Orwell's books shall reappear in Brazilian bookshops accompanied by a handful of projects, many of them aiming at bringing distinct perspectives into play so as to reassess this author's participation within our literary system. When one takes into account descriptive studies, as well as the polysystems field in Translation Studies (LAMBERT, 2011), in many occasions s/he fails to acknowledge that there is an organic and invisible "deal" for certain translations to get in and spread throughout a certain cultural system. When Bruno Latour (2011) brings the actor-network theory into play, he opens up room for us to reflect upon such condition – shedding a more critical light on the role that literary translations play and how exactly such role is played. This is to say: there is much more to TS than simply "the text" and its equivalences. Having said that, my proposal is to reflect upon the social aspects of the first Brazilian translation of *Animal farm*: a fairy tale (1945), carried out by an army lieutenant in the year of our military coup d'état (1964), in parallel with a reflection upon my retranslation of such novel, which is to be published in 2021.

Keywords: George Orwell, "Animal farm", translation studies, Brazilian translation